

High-quality new knowledge effectively diffused through open science

20-25% cut in energy demand

45-55% reduction in energy system emissions

Innovation-based growth through R&I investments

Making energy supply cleaner, more competitive, and secure.

Energy integration benefits will be demonstrated in:

Port of Sines
Portugal

Høje-Taastrup Municipality
Denmark

Dokken Area in Bergen
Norway

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